

Unitarian Universalism

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Entry tags: Liberal Religion, Secularism, American Christianity, North American Religions, Religious Group, Protestantism

In the United States, the American Unitarian Association and Universalist Church of America merged in 1961 to form the Unitarian Universalist Association. Although Unitarians and Universalists were nominally Christian denominations, the Unitarian Universalists subsequently adopted the principles of free faith, in which each member unites in seeking truth and affirms each other's worth without the guidance of a particular doctrine or divinity. Now described as a liberal religious movement or post-Christian, Unitarian Universalists hold many different theological opinions and operate as a radically non-creedal body. There is a wide diversity of congregational structures and organizations and each group may self-describe as a church, society, fellowship, or temple, among other identifiers. Each Unitarian Universalist congregation is distinct in tone and content of worship, even within the same city, but each is guided by the seven Principles and six Sources. The Principles serve as a unifying guide and affirm the inherent worth and dignity of every person; justice, equity, and compassion in human relations; acceptance of one another and encouragement to spiritual growth; a free and responsible search for truth and meaning; the right of conscience and the use of the democratic process without congregations and in society at large; the goal of world community with peace, liberty and justice for all; and respect for the interdependent web of all existence of which we are part. The Sources include direct experience, words and deeds of prophetic people, wisdom from the world's religions, Jewish and Christian teachings to love our neighbors, humanist teachings and the guidance of reason and science, and spiritual teachings drawn from Earth-centered traditions. As a result, congregants draw from religious traditions such as Christianity or Judaism; spiritual practices of meditation, yoga, and connection to nature; and other influences including Paganism and New Age beliefs. Unitarian Universalists express strong commitment to social justice and action. They contend that spirituality and community extend beyond the walls of the congregation and must be lived in the world, and this message has spread beyond the borders of North America. The International Council of Unitarians and Universalists provides a network of organizations worldwide, including congregations throughout Africa; Europe and the UK; Australia and New Zealand; India, the Philippines, Hong Kong, and Indonesia; the Caribbean; and in Central and South America. However, the tradition remains deeply affiliated with the West, as estimates indicate over 60% of Unitarian Universalists are in the United States and approximately 30% in Europe.

Date Range: 1825 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Europe, North America, Canada, United States of America, Africa, Eastern Africa, Southern Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean, Caribbean, Puerto Rico, Scotland, England, Canada, Cuba

Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations associated with the International Council of Unitarians and Universalists (ICUU), 2020

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: A Documentary History of Unitarian Universalism: Volume One by Dan McKanan (2017)
- Source 2: A Documentary History of Unitarian Universalism: Volume Two by Dan McKanan (2017)
- Source 3: An Introduction to the Unitarian and Universalist Traditions by Andrea Greenwood and Mark Harris

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Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.uua.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Unitarian Universalist Association website
- Source 2 URL: <https://commons.trincoll.edu/aris/files/2012/05/unitarians9008.pdf>
- Source 2 Description: Unitarian-Universalists in the United States 1900-2008: Socio-demographic Trends and Religious Patterns; Pls: Barry Kosmin & Ariela Keysar
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-3UYWnngiEo>
- Source 3 Description: We Are Unitarian Universalists, video by Unitarian Universalist Association

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General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

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Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

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Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists strive for pluralistic inclusion. Areas in which these congregations are found vary in their accommodation, but Unitarian Universalism underscores the importance of openness and willingness to accept others.

<https://revnaomiking.tumblr.com/post/10859197371/our-unitarian-universalist-good-news-affirms>

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↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

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↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

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– Yes

Notes: In some areas of the world there are instances of violent conflict against many groups of people, including Unitarian Universalists. For example, during political and governmental violence in Burundi in 2015, a leader within the Unitarian Universalist was pressed with active charges from the government. As a result, it was necessary for Burundi Unitarians to join the large number of people fleeing from the region. In 2008 in the United States, a man opened fire on a Unitarian Universalist church in Tennessee, killing two people and wounding six. His aim was to "kill liberals" and die in a shootout with the police. This intent seemed to indicate he targeted the Unitarian church for their political beliefs.

Reference: Lakin, Matt, and J. J. Stambaugh. "One Year After the TVUU Church Shooting". Knoxville News Sentinel, July 26, 2009. <http://archive.knoxnews.com/news/local/one-year-after-the-tvuu-church-shooting-ep-409779471-359295901.html/>.

Reference: Former Staff. "Crisis Situation for Unitarians in Burundi". International Council of Unitarians and Universalists, n.d.. <https://icuu.net/2015/11/24/crisis-situation-for-unitarians-in-burundi-2/>.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

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Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

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↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

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↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: In my fieldwork at the Unitarian Society, I attended a New Member Orientation in which people who had filled out the appropriate paperwork would learn more about becoming a member of the congregation. The paperwork included answering a series of questions for a personal biography (to be included on the website), a questionnaire of interests (choir, volunteering, etc.), and a pledge form for monetary donations. In the New Member Orientation we learned more about the seven Principles and if you affirmed those precepts you were accepted as a member through personal declaration.

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↳ Assigned by class:

– No

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↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalists do not uniformly use age as a method of membership, but in Transylvanian congregations adolescents between the ages of 14 and 16 are confirmed in the church and become independent members.

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↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

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↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

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Assigned by some other factor:

– No

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Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Officially, Unitarian Universalists do not require members to proselytize. However, in the United States in the past decade there have been media campaigns to spread the word about their open and inclusive beliefs. <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-2006-oct-28-me-unitarians28-story.html>

Reference: Haldane, David. "Bearing Witness to a Sea Change in Unitarian Practice". Los Angeles Times, October 28, 2006. <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-2006-oct-28-me-unitarians28-story.html>.

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Does the religion have official political support

– No

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Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The concept of apostasy or exiting Unitarian Universalism is nuanced because, on the basis of belief or theology, you're equally as likely to have people to check Buddhism or Christianity or Atheist if asked about their religious belief. For example, how would you classify a "Jew-ish Unitarian Universalist" (<https://twitter.com/rkfmiller>) with respect to group membership? So a lot of it depends on how you measure the concept of apostasy. Is it leaving the congregation, leaving your personal faith, or both? Apostasy as understood as rebellion against the truth in a Unitarian Universalist context may mean turning away from your personal truth like peace and justice, combating climate change, or welcoming immigrants.

Reference: Menk, Russ. "Apostasy Temptation". Unitarian Universalist Fellowship of Santa Cruz County, May 29, 2018. <https://uufsc.org/site/apostasy-temptation/>.

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 600000

Notes: Because calculating the number of adherents is challenging in liberal traditions like Unitarian Universalism, where membership is voluntary and there aren't theological stakes tied to attendance, the numbers are not completely clear. The 2008 American Religious Identification Survey (ARIS) and The Faith Communities Today (FACT) surveys estimate that in 2008 there were approximately 586,000 UUs in the United States. However, the International Council of Unitarians and Universalists (ICUU) reported in 2012 that there were 343,473 UU members worldwide, which includes the United States. This disparity is rooted in the distinction between official membership and self-reported membership. In the United States, Unitarian Universalism originated in the Northeast states, which is historically where the greatest numbers of Unitarian Universalists resided. In 2008, there was an increase in both the South, although still underrepresented with respect to the general population, (see <https://twitter.com/FirstUUNash> for a thriving Southern congregation) and the West (see <https://twitter.com/UUSantaMonica> for a popular Western congregation).

Reference: Kosmin, Barry A., and Ariela Keysar. "Unitarian-universalists in the United States 1990-2008: Sociodemographic Trends and Religious Patterns". Institute for the Study of Secularism in Society and Culture, January 1, 2009. <https://commons.trincoll.edu/aris/files/2012/05/unitarians9008.pdf>.

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.25

Notes: This estimation comes from the American Religious Identification Survey (2008), which is calculated based on the US population and does not account for populations in places like India or China, in which UUs likely represent an even more minute sample. However, Transylvania has the largest concentration of Unitarians. Five percent of the general population of Transylvania is Unitarian and a full quarter of the linguistic-ethnic Hungarians living there are Unitarians.

Reference: Kosmin, Barry A., and Ariela Keysar. "Unitarian-universalists in the United States 1990-2008: Sociodemographic Trends and Religious Patterns". Institute for the Study of Secularism in Society and Culture, January 1, 2009. <https://commons.trincoll.edu/aris/files/2012/05/unitarians9008.pdf>.

Reference: Greenwood, Andrea, and Mark W. Harris. *An Introduction to the Unitarian and Universalist Traditions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.

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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative

and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists originated in Protestant Christianity and do rely on the Christian Bible as a sacred text. In some places outside of North America such as Transylvania, Great Britain, and Ireland, Unitarian Universalists consider themselves Christian and use the Christian Bible as the primary sacred text. However, they also look to additional sources for inspiration from scripture of other traditions like the Tao Te-Ching and the Bhagavad Gita to poetry and art to scientific findings. They treat all of these sources as wells of wisdom, although not necessarily divinely inspired.

Reference: Greenwood, Andrea, and Mark W. Harris. *An Introduction to the Unitarian and Universalist Traditions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.

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↳ Are they written:

– Yes

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↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

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↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: In North America particularly, the sacred texts are understood to be works of non-divine, but very wise, people.

Reference: Unitarian Association Universalist. “Sources of Our Living Tradition”. Unitarian Universalist Association, n.d.. <https://www.uua.org/beliefs/what-we-believe/sources>.

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↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

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↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

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↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

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↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

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↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

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↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

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Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

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Is iconography present:

– Yes

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↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

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↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

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↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

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↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

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↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

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↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

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↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

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↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

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↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: The primary iconography of the Unitarian Universalist tradition is the flaming chalice. The chalice represents different things to different congregations and individuals, including reason, community, and hope. The chalice is primarily used during worship services, although a more modern logo that represented the chalice was created in 2014 and used for stickers, t-shirts, and other printed content. The file attached shows the flaming chalice as represented on U.S. Military burial headstones. Transylvanian Unitarianism, a much older tradition that is part of the origins of Unitarianism, is symbolized by a serpent and a dove.

Reference: UUA Program and Strategy: Outreach Office, and Outreach Office. "UUA Logo and Graphics". Unitarian Universalist Association, n.d..
<https://www.uua.org/leadership/library/uua-logo>.

Reference: Greenwood, Andrea, and Mark W. Harris. *An Introduction to the Unitarian and Universalist Traditions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.

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↳ Humans:

– No

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↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

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Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

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Are pilgrimages present:

– No

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Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Many Unitarian Universalists believe in a distinction between the body and mind or spirit, but this is not part of the doctrine of the organization. In my fieldwork there were several lectures given about Near Death Experiences, which were often accounts of validation that the mind can leave the body during these liminal moments. However, a number of Unitarian Universalists identify as atheists or materialists and do not subscribe to a mind/spirit distinction. They believe that when the body dies consciousness is extinguished.

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Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

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Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

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– No

Notes: Because Unitarian Universalists doctrine does not dictate an answer to the body/mind divide, there are also avowed materialists among the congregations. In my research I encountered many people who believed that the brain/body was the mind and that they were not fundamentally able to be separated.

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Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Again, it is important to note that the Unitarian Universalist organizations do not specify beliefs or doctrine with respect to the afterlife. In my interviews with leadership within the UUA, they specified that their role was to facilitate individuals' personal beliefs about life after death and to not direct them in any particular direction. The only specific item that they would not support is a negative conception of afterlife that was harmful to the person (e.g. a belief in Hell). https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oF_qKz7etr0

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Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

– No

Notes: Some Unitarian Universalists do not believe in an afterlife. I interviewed several people who believed that when our physical bodies die we return to nothing. Unitarian Universalism only takes the stance that the afterlife is not negative, but does not affirm any particular form of afterlife beyond that. <https://twitter.com/FlyingRatLady/status/1187298455947042827?s=20>

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Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: Some individuals within the Unitarian Universalist community self-describe as Buddhists and believe in reincarnation in that respect, but others believe in a more Westernized version of reincarnation. This is not a tenet of Unitarian Universalist doctrine, but is a common belief within the community. On online forums I have seen examples of Unitarian Universalists who believe all those who are worthy go to heaven and those that are not are reincarnated on earth: https://www.reddit.com/r/UUreddit/comments/ffivla/thoughts_on_reincarnation/

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– No

Notes: While some people do subscribe to notions of reincarnation, some people believe in a final resting place for an afterlife and others believe that nothing happens after death. Unitarian Universalist

doctrine does not support or deny belief in reincarnation, but allows individuals to choose their own belief.

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Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalist doctrine does not provide guidance for special treatment for adherents' corpses. However, Unitarians in the nineteenth century were among the most vocal supporters of cremation as a form of disposition. Contemporary Unitarian Universalists seem to be more focused on the preparations for death in a practical sense. At my fieldwork site they offered a course called "Aging Well," which included instructions for how to create a will and make logistical choices about burial and services after you die.

Reference: Prothero, Stephen. *Purified by Fire: A History of Cremation in America*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 2001.

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Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

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Are grave goods present:

– No

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Are formal burials present:

– Yes

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As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

Notes: Although not prohibited or encouraged by Unitarian Universalist doctrine, I have not seen cenotaphs as a form of memorialization, but it is certainly a possibility.

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↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials in a cemetery are still common among the population in the United States, but cremation has recently become more popular overall and is more popular among Unitarian Universalists. The group does not specify one form of disposition, and is open to all kinds of formal and informal ceremonies.

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↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: As with cemetery burial, this form of disposition is likely less common among Unitarian Universalists, who tend to favor cremation, but the group doctrine does not specify that a family tomb-crypt would not be acceptable.

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↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

Notes: In the United States the restrictions around interment in a domestic sphere are more strict, so legally this would be more of a challenge. However, I don't know what the legal practices are in other countries. Unitarian Universalism does not have specific doctrine that specifies that this would be unacceptable.

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↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Cremation and burial of cremains

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are more likely to cremate individuals in the United States than the general population. This is often accompanied with a Celebration of Life or Memorial Service that occurs some period of time after the cremation.

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Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

— No

Notes: Unitarianism emerged from Congregationalism (a form of Protestant Christianity). One of the primary distinctions that spurred separation was the Unitarians' belief that the Christian God is one being as opposed to a trinity (Father, Son, and Holy Ghost). As Unitarianism developed in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries it became more influenced by humanism and other liberal religious traditions, eventually expanding its message of inclusion to the point of not affirming the belief in a Christian God. The Seven Principles of Unitarian Universalism (originally adopted in the 1959 Constitution of the Unitarian Universalist Association) do not profess belief in supernatural beings. The Principles do not serve as dogma or doctrine, but are guidelines for how to treat others and united goals. Within the congregation, individuals do affirm belief in a Christian God, Buddha, ghosts, ancestors, Pagan gods, other beings or no supernatural beings at all. All of these beliefs are encouraged and tolerated under the 3rd Principle of accepting one another and encouraging spiritual growth within congregations. For example, I spoke with a woman in my fieldwork who joined the Unitarian Universalist church after attending a yoga course here. She was concerned because she grew up Presbyterian and didn't believe she would like going to church again. She thought there may be a problem because she "loved Jesus and loved the Buddha," but found that her beliefs were completely accepted within Unitarian Universalism. Although belief in and acknowledgment of supernatural beings is absent, the congregation with which I did my fieldwork did honor humanists and human-rights activists. Below the stained-glass windows of the Society, plates were engraved with names including Ralph Waldo Emerson, Henry David Thoreau, and Julia Ward Howe, among others. While not technically worshiped, these thinkers are given places of honor and are often the source of readings.

Reference: McKanan, Dan, ed.. *A Documentary History of Unitarian Universalism: Volume Two from 1900 to the Present*. Edited by Dan McKanan. Vol. 2. Boston: Skinner House Books, 2017.

Reference: Unitarian Association Universalist. "The Seven Principles". Unitarian Universalist Association, n.d.. <https://www.uua.org/beliefs/what-we-believe/principles>.

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Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

— No

Notes: Unitarian Universalism does not subscribe to belief in supernatural beings, but individuals are encouraged and welcome to do so. Instead, UUs look to human morality and ethics as guiding forces. Within congregations you may have individuals that do believe in supernatural monitoring, but this is not a tenet of UU guidance.

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Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

— No

Notes: Unitarian Universalist Principles include a belief in the inherent worth and dignity of every

person. In interviews with leadership within UU congregations, each leader indicated that they help facilitate growth and development within a spiritual path, but would step in to help the individual reconstruct or rethink maladaptive or negative beliefs, including belief in a vengeful or angry being. Individuals within UU may believe in supernatural beings punishing humans, but this belief is likely rare based on the UU disavowal of Hell.

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Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: Individuals within congregations may believe in a benevolent supernatural being, but this is not a position taken by the Unitarian Universalist group.

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Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: In the nineteenth century, both Unitarians and Universalists began to break with mainline Protestant Christian beliefs in the trinity of God (God, Jesus, Holy Ghost). Unlike other groups derived from Protestant Christianity, Unitarian Universalists do not officially believe that Jesus Christ is a messianic figure. Within the UU congregations, Jesus is a spiritual teacher and moral guide, but not divine. <https://www.uua.org/beliefs/what-we-believe/beliefs/christianity/views-jesus>
<https://twitter.com/karigottfried/status/1292288286124171265?s=20> In Transylvania, the connection with Protestant Christianity is stronger and their congregations identify as theistic in the sense that they believe in Jesus as a teacher, master, and prophet. However, even in this group Jesus is not considered divine.

Reference: Former Staff. "Transylvanian Unitarianism". International Council of Unitarians and Universalists, n.d.. <https://icuu.net/2015/11/11/transylvanian-unitarianism/>.

Reference: Albanese, Catherine. *A Republic of Mind and Spirit: A Cultural History of American Metaphysical Religion*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2007.

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Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: General social norms within Unitarian Universalism are principles of openness, pluralism, and the belief in justice, equity, and compassion in human relations. Social norms include activism and attention to social justice causes.

https://www.reddit.com/r/UUreddit/comments/i93ss1/in_a_simple_conversational_manner_how_do_you/

This was demonstrated to me during my fieldwork when a congregant welcomed me and asked where I was from. When I said that I was from North Carolina, she affirmed that Unitarian Universalists were not nearly as judgmental as many spiritualities and religions in the South. During that same service in Spring 2019, the minister described the Society as an "loving community of seekers" who come there to find their religious and spiritual home.

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Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalism affirms a universal moral code of acceptance and openness. There is little distinction between people and high priority and value given to treating all people equally.

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Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– No

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– No

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– No

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– No

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– No

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– No

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Attention to the democratic process; respect for all existence

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The Unitarian Universalist Association provides comprehensive sex education that is fact-based and underscores values of self worth, sexual health, responsibility, and justice and inclusivity. Instead of focusing on an abstinence-based approach, the UUA encourages developing decision-making and self-expression. <https://twitter.com/SorayaMcDonald/status/1259096622648213511?s=20>

Reference: Unitarian Association Universalist. "Our Whole Lives: Lifespan Sexuality Education". Unitarian Universalist Association, n.d.. <https://www.uua.org/re/owl>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Within Unitarian Universalism there is no doctrine that specifies a requirement to attend services, but this is implicitly encouraged as part of your spiritual growth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalism can be described as an ethical rather than a creedal tradition. With no distinguishing characteristics in the realm of belief and doctrine, Unitarian Universalists find authority in the individual conscience, guided by the Seven Principles. The Seven Principles are the moral guides within the Unitarian Universalist community. To become a member you learn and accept the Seven Principles, which include affirming the inherent worth and dignity of every person; justice, equity, and compassion in human relations; acceptance of one another and encouragement to spiritual growth in our congregations; a free and responsible search for truth and meaning; the right of conscience and the use of the democratic process without our congregations and in society at large; the goal of world community with peace, liberty, and justice for all; and respect for the interdependent web of all existence of which we are a part.

Reference: Unitarian Association Universalist. "The Seven Principles". Unitarian Universalist Association, n.d.. <https://www.uua.org/beliefs/what-we-believe/principles>.

Reference: Greenwood, Andrea, and Mark W. Harris. *An Introduction to the Unitarian and Universalist Traditions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are part of the liberal religious traditions that allow a wide range of beliefs

within their group. Based on my research, many people within UU congregations would identify as Buddhist, Pagan, Christian, or Atheist ahead of Unitarian Universalist, which indicates that there is not a clear line to distinguish in-group versus out-group in general.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Membership does not require any particular small-scale rituals, but practices are encouraged as part of members' spiritual development. Small-scale rituals performed by UUs may include meditation, prayer, journaling, or hiking in nature.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are not required to participate in any large-scale rituals, but there are congregation-wide celebrations and passages that are optional. These include child dedication ceremonies, coming of age ceremonies, bridging ceremonies, weddings, and memorial services. None of these are required as a tenet of membership. During my fieldwork I attended a service in which two children (infants) were dedicated to the church. Each family read a short prepared speech, one of which alluded to the four elements (earth, water, air, fire). The families pledged to keep the children safe and to help them grow in the church. The minister then took each child in turn and blessed them with water, heat from the fire (for intellect), earth from the garden (for strength), and wind, or breath from her (for the breath of life.) Then, the congregation recited a response about their dedication to supporting the children

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The individual congregations belong to an Association.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are committed to social justice and action, including combating hunger and famine both domestically and internationally. Individual congregations gather donations of food and other needed items locally as well as partnering with other organizations to aid in famine relief.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Unitarian Universalist Service Committee (UUSC) is a nonprofit, nonsectarian organization that partners with Unitarian Universalist congregations to offer aid to the international community. Through this organization, Unitarian Universalists have contributed to famine relief and other social causes around the world. One notable example is their efforts in Ethiopia in 1984. <https://twitter.com/UUSC> This is just one such organization that Unitarian Universalists partner with to provide aid.

Reference: Unitarian Service Committee Universalist. "About UUSC". Unitarian Universalist Service Committee, n.d.. <https://www.uusc.org/about-uusc/>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalists do not sponsor individuals or provide poverty relief directly to individuals at the congregational level. They support local organizations or volunteer to aid in these endeavors. The larger group, like the Unitarian Universalist Association in the United States, partners with other kinds of organizations to provide this aid.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the 1820s, the American Unitarian Association authorized Joseph Tuckerman, a Unitarian from Massachusetts, to begin a Ministry to the Poor which is today called the Unitarian Universalist Urban Ministry (UUUM). The UUUM provides after-school tutoring, summer and weekend youth programs, a shelter for victims of domestic violence, and a food pantry that caters to the needs of the Asian poor and elderly. The UUUM is supported by sixty congregations through their volunteering, donations, and fundraising. It is just one such example of a partner organization that provides assistance to the poor and in-need.

Reference: Greenwood, Andrea, and Mark W. Harris. *An Introduction to the Unitarian and Universalist Traditions*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2011.

Reference: Unitarian Universalist Ministry Urban. "What We Do". Unitarian Universalist Urban Ministry, n.d.. http://www.uuum.org/?page_id=145.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Two theological schools in the United States are affiliated with the Unitarian Universalist Association: Star King School for the Ministry and Meadville Lombard Theological School. Other theological schools that have a heavy Unitarian Universalist presence include Boston University, Harvard University, and Yale University School, among others. The UUA is not affiliated nor does it sponsor any primary or secondary education outside of ministerial training.

Reference: Unitarian Association Universalist. "Theological Schools Offering a Masters of Divinity Degree". Unitarian Universalist Association, n.d..
<https://www.uua.org/careers/ministers/becoming/theological-schools>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

– No

Notes: Although no primary and secondary schools are sponsored by the Unitarian Universalists, pre-primary schools are available in the United States and in countries such as India, where nearly all of the congregations offer non-sectarian pre-primary education for children in the village. At my fieldwork site there was also religious education offered at all ages, from young children to adult. Children's Religious Education (also known as "Sunday School" in Protestant denominations) is offered on Sundays alongside the main service. The children are taught progressive Unitarian Universalist values and religious literacy of the world's great faiths. Groups are also offered for teenagers and young adults to learn more. These religious education courses are supplemental to the secular education received outside of the Society. <https://www.facebook.com/groups/UURED> In my fieldwork I also noted a strong emphasis on self-development and continued education. The Society had an active library that had titles that ranged from self-help such as Sean Covey's *The 7 Habits of Highly Effective People*, to social issues like *Hillbilly Elegy* by J.D. Vance and science like Neil deGrasse Tyson's *Astrophysics for People in a Hurry*.

Reference: Former Staff. "India - Khasi Hills Unitarianism". International Council of Unitarians and Universalists, n.d.. <https://icuu.net/2015/11/11/india-khasi-hills-unitarianism/>.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Members of Unitarian Universalist congregations are encouraged to continue their education at private or public institutions from childhood to adulthood. Higher levels of education attainment are common in Unitarian Universalist congregations. According to the American Religious Identification Survey in 2008, Unitarian Universalists have attained higher levels of education than the general population in the United States. In 2008, 25% of Unitarian Universalists had post-graduate qualifications compared to 8% of the U.S. general population. The proportion is also much higher for college, with 28% of Unitarian Universalists attending college compared to 17% of the U.S. population. On the other side of the scale, the highest levels of attainment includes only 5% of Unitarian Universalists who have completed less than high school and 6% who completed high school or

technical school compared to 17% and 31% of the of the U.S. general population, respectively.

Reference: Kosmin, Barry A., and Ariela Keysar. "Unitarian-universalists in the United States 1990-2008: Sociodemographic Trends and Religious Patterns". Institute for the Study of Secularism in Society and Culture, January 1, 2009. <https://commons.trincoll.edu/aris/files/2012/05/unitarians9008.pdf>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalists emerged from Congregationalism and have continued to practice a congregational polity in which each member is entitled to weigh in and vote on issues. In May 2019 I attended a Budget Town Hall at the local Unitarian Universalist congregation. Information was displayed on a projector and congregants were invited to ask questions and offer discussion about the budget. The congregations do support a staff and Board of Trustees, but the process is very democratic in both practical and spiritual affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Although not available in every congregation, some Unitarian Universalist congregations house a Food Bank or Food Pantry that is available to the public. In Medford, Massachusetts, The Community Cupboard Food Pantry has been in the church since its creation in the early 1990s. The Food Pantry offers food for people in need weekly. Other congregations temporarily house Food Bank supplies and continue their services during times of hardship or transition, like at the Unitarian Universalist Society of Wellesley Hills: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MxgwdKr9rcY>

Reference: UU Medford Church. "Food Pantry". The Unitarian Universalist Church of Medford, n.d.. <https://uumedford.org/connection/food-pantry/>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Working with Food Banks and other organizations within communities is part of Unitarian Universalists' commitment to social justice and volunteer work. Many Unitarian Universalist congregations and members volunteer with and donate to food banks in their local area. For example, the Unitarian Universalist Society of Geneva in Geneva, Illinois has a Food Bank Group that meets monthly to volunteer at the Northern Illinois Food Bank. Other outreach includes monthly collection and donations of food to local Food Pantries. The Unitarian Universalist Church of Fresno donates to the Valley Children's Hospital Food Pantry and the Food Pantry at Wesley United Methodist Church on the third Sunday of each month.

Reference: UU Of Geneva Society. "Food Bank Group". Unitarian Universalist Society of Geneva, n.d.. <http://www.uusg.org/food-bank>.

Reference: UU of Fresno Church. "Food Pantry Donations". Unitarian Universalist Church of Fresno, n.d.. <https://uufresno.org/food-pantry/>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: During Unitarian Universalist services an offering is requested. At the congregation I attended, 25% of the offering is donated to a non-profit organization supporting a social cause, which rotates monthly. The month I attended 25% of the proceeds went to Black Lives of Unitarian Universalism. These donations are optional and not required as a part of attendance. Members are encouraged to pledge a certain amount of monetary giving, based on their personal circumstances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are not exempted from local, state, and federal taxes, but are not subject to any overarching religious or spiritual group taxation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists, like any religious group operating in a nation-state, are often subject to the laws and law enforcement of that country. In the United States, recent interactions with law enforcement has resulted in the First Unitarian Church of Portland, Oregon joining with others in filing a lawsuit in July 2020 against the U.S. Department of Homeland Security, U.S. Customs and Border Protection, Federal Protective Service, and the U.S. Marshals Service. The lawsuit accuses the agencies

of violating the limitations of the U.S. Constitution.

Reference: Katu, Staff. "New Lawsuit Filed Accuses Federal Law Enforcement of Violating Tenth Amendment in Portland". KATU. July 21, 2020. <https://katu.com/news/local/new-lawsuit-filed-accuses-federal-law-enforcement-of-violating-tenth-amendment-in-portland>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are subject to the judicial system of their resident country. For example, in the United States in 2017 four aid volunteers left food and water for undocumented immigrants to find and were found guilty of breaking federal law. In 2020, their conviction was overturned because the US District Judge ruled that, because they were a part of the No More Deaths ministry of the Unitarian Universalist Church of Tucson (<https://twitter.com/NoMoreDeaths>), were acting on their sincere religious beliefs. This is just a small example of the way in which Unitarian Universalists interaction with the judicial system can be impacted by their faith.

Reference: Kaur, Harmeet. "A Judge Overturned the Convictions of Four Volunteers Who Left Food and Water for Migrants in the Desert". CNN, February 6, 2020. <https://www.cnn.com/2020/02/06/us/arizona-aid-volunteers-reverse-convictions-trnd/index.html>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are subject to the punishment of their country's government and legal system, not on the basis of their faith, but on the basis of their citizenship. The nature of these punishments vary based on the nation. For example, in the United States the death penalty is still a potential form of punishment for certain crimes for any U.S. Citizen.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists are subject to the legal code of their country's government and legal system, not on the basis of their faith, but on the basis of their citizenship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Unitarian Universalists may participate in local or state-sponsored military. UUs have no prohibitions against participation in these types of organizations, but Unitarian Universalism does not sponsor or mandate participation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: For example, as citizens of a nation, such as the United States or Canada, Unitarian Universalists are subject to the protection of the state government military.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Unitarian Universalists operate out of a general Gregorian Calendar. They celebrate a wide variety of religious and spiritual holidays, including many of the Jewish and Christian holidays alongside a variety of Pagan holidays, but have no formalized calendar specific to Unitarian Universalism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Unitarian Universalist Organizations and Congregations

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